

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B346
Date: 19 February 2008
Take Off: 17:24:15Z
Landing: 22:23:59Z
Flight Time 4h 59m 44

Campaign: CLPX II

Operating Area: Brooks Range and North Slope Ground Sites, Alaska

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight
3	CCM1	Gaynor Ottoway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chem / AVAPS / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Jim Crawford	FAAM
8	SWS	Ian Rule	Met Office
9	CVI / Nephelometers	Rob King	Met Office
10	DEIMOS	Dave Pollard	Met Office
11	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
12	Mission Scientist 2	Jonathan Taylor	Met Office

Flight Track:

B346 Track 19-FEB-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B346

Date: 19 February 2008

Project: CLPX II

Location: Barrow Range and North Slope, Alaska

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
164700		Start-Up	0.89 kft	318 64 49.58N,	147,50.98W
165941		Pan Posn	0.89 kft	216 64'49.60N,	147'50.98W
170709		ASP	0.89 kft	216	Open
172152		Video	0.90 kft	050	Start FFC & DFC1
172415		T/O	1.6 kft	213	Fairbanks
180318	180903	Profile 1	16.3 - 10.4 kft	323	16k-10k', QNH 29.58"
181238	181735	Profile 1	10.3 - 5.9 kft	328	10k-5.6k', Q29.57
181535		Event	7.7 kft	352	Gentle Turn
181549		Video	7.4 kft	002	Switch FFC to UFC
181953	182257	Run 1	5.9 kft	073	C2-D2, 5.6k'
182313	182507	Profile 2	5.9 - 4.4 kft	064	Turning
182507	183246	Run 2	4.4 - 4.3 kft	009	E2-F2, 4k'
183602		Event	4.4 kft	199	Heimann Cal
184029		Event	4.4 kft	196	Zero JW & Nevz
184658	185010	Run 3	4.1 - 3.8 kft	065	C2-D2, 3.6k'
185131		Video	3.2 kft	006	Start UFC & DFC2
185207	185957	Run 4	2.9 - 2.4 kft	002	E2-F2, 2.1k'
190745		Event	5.3 kft	197	Heimann Cal
191152		Ground Site	5.3 kft	197	68,39',48.9"N, 149,8',45.3"W
191417	191715	Run 5	4.4 - 3.9 kft	063	C1-D1, 3.7k'
192008	192735	Run 6	3.1 - 3.0 kft	359	E1-F1, 2.8k'
192800		Video	3.2 kft	312	Switch UFC to FFC
193006		Event	5.4 kft	201	Heimann Cal
194143	194444	Run 7	4.3 - 3.8 kft	067	C3-D3, 3.6k'
194706	195437	Run 8	3.1 - 2.3 kft	000	E3-F3, 2k'
195808		Event	5.3 kft	198	Heimann Cal
200902	201154	Run 9	4.2 - 3.9 kft	060	C-D,3.7K'
201421	202206	Run 10	3.0 - 2.2 kft	009	H-G, 2k'
202228	204425	Profile 3	2.2 - 23.9 kft	339	
203105		Video	10.3 kft	323	Start FFC & DFC3
204629	210549	Profile 3	24.0 - 35.0 kft	144	To F
205301		Event	29.9 kft	157	Contrailing
210557	211149	Run 11	35.0 kft	189	F2-E2
210634		Sonde	35.0 kft	189	Launch #01
210937		Sonde	35.0 kft	189	Launch #02
211309	211557	Run 11.2	35.1 - 35.0 kft	227	D2-C2
211316		Sonde	35.1 kft	227	Launch #03
211600		Event	35.1 kft		Satellite overpass
212605	212927	Run 11.3	35.0 kft	230	Not F2-E2!!!
212631		Sonde	35.1 kft	221	Launch #04
212903		Sonde	35.0 kft	188	Launch #05
220416		Video	29.0 kft	179	End of Tapes
221523		ASP	9.3 kft	170	Closed
222359		Land	1.1 kft	336	Fairbanks
223004		Shutdown	1.1 kft	311	64'49.58N,147'50.98W

B346 Track 19-FEB-08

FAAM Sortie Brief

Project: CLPX-II.

Sortie 1: Ground transect overflight with sonde dropping.

Flight Number: B346

Date: 19/02/2008

Scientific objectives: To measure emissivities along the ground transects where snow hydrologists are making detailed measurements of snow properties. The sonde dropping run is for establishing the atmospheric temperature and humidity profiles and the variance of such profiles to assist in modeling of the atmospheric radiative transfer.

Location: Over the Brooks Range and North Slope of Alaska.

Weather conditions: Hopefully cloud free. Much of the decision to fly from a science perspective will come from the ground crew participation.

Flight Pattern: The flight will consist of the overpass of two ground sites as straight and level runs (SLRs) at low level and high level. Sondes will be dropped during the high level runs. The ends of the runs are given by fixed way points.

Point	Latitude	Longitude
C	68 34.92	149 29.968
D	68 39.367	148 59.92
C1	68 34.683	149 29.3
D1	68 39.667	148 59.267
C2	68 35.117	149 29.817
D2	68 40.083	148 59.917
C3	68 35.533	149 30.333
D3	68 40.667	149 00.367
E	68 46.263	148 53.007
F	69 13.691	148 55.378
E1	68 46.09	148 54.349
F1	69 13.191	148 56.119
E2	68 46.114	148 55.529
F2	69 13.191	148 57.365
E3	68 46.138	148 56.709
F3	69 13.191	148 58.546
H	68 46.206	148 58.053
G	69 13.632	149 00.531

Sortie detail:

1. T+0. (0830L) Take off and transit to operating area. Profile during transit to 2000' agl arriving at point C2. (45 min)
2. T+45. (0915L) Carry out SLR at 2000' agl from C2 to D2. (4 min)
3. T+49. (0919L) Reposition to point E2. (3 min)
4. T+52. (0922L) Carry out SLR at 2000' agl from E2 to F2. (8 min)
5. T+60. (0930L) Reposition to point C2 arriving at minimum safety altitude (MSA). (15 min)
6. T+75. (0945L) Carry out SLR at MSA from C2 to D2. (4 min)
7. T+79. (0949L) Reposition to point E2. (3 min)
8. T+82. (0952L) Carry out SLR at MSA from E2 to F2. (8 min)
9. T+90. (1000L) Reposition to point C1 arriving at MSA. (15 min)
10. T+105. (1015L) Carry out SLR at MSA from C1 to D1. (4 min)
11. T+109. (1019L) Reposition to point E1. (3 min)
12. T+112. (1022L) Carry out SLR at MSA from E1 to F1. (8 min)
13. T+120. (1030L) Reposition to point C3. (15 min)
14. T+135. (1045L) Carry out SLR at MSA from C3 to D3. (4 min)
15. T+139. (1049L) Reposition to point E3. (3 min)
16. T+142. (1052L) Carry out SLR at MSA from E3 to F3. (8 min)
17. T+150. (1100L) Reposition to point C. (15 min)

18. T+165. (1115L) Carry out SLR at MSA from C to D. (4 min)
19. T+169. (1119L) Reposition to point H. (3 min)
20. T+172. (1122L) Carry out SLR at MSA from H to G. (8 min)
21. T+180. (1130L) Profile up to Max Altitude arriving at point F2. (35 min)
22. T+215. (1205L) Carry out SLR from F2 to E2 at max alt. dropping two sondes (0, 3 min timings)(6 min)
23. T+221. (1211L) Reposition to point D2. (2 min)
24. T+223. (1213L) Carry out SLR from D2 to C2 at max alt. dropping one sondes (0 min timing)(3 min)
25. T+226. (1216L) Reposition to point F2. (10 min)
26. T+236. (1226L) Carry out SLR from F2 to E2 at max alt. dropping one sondes (0 min timings)(6 min)
27. T+242. (1232L) Reposition to point D2. (2 min)
28. T+244. (1234L) Carry out SLR from D2 to C2 at max alt. dropping one sondes (0 min timings)(3 min)
29. T+247. (1237L) Transit back to Fairbanks (60 min)
30. T+307. (1337L) Land.

B346 – Sortie Debrief

Mission Scientist: Chawn Harlow

19/02/08

Campaign: CLPX-II

The objective of this sortie was to measure the emissivity of the snow covered land in the sites where snow hydrologists were monitoring snow physical parameters. This requires skies that are relatively cloud free. The key instruments are MARSS and Deimos, ARIES, the Heimann, the radar altimeter and the drop sondes.

After transit to the operating area, conditions were found to be ideal with clear skies throughout the low level runs. Ten straight and level runs (SLRs) were carried out over the field sites in the pattern outlined in the sortie brief. These were at altitudes between 2000' and 5600' ASL. The aircraft then profiled up to FL350 where a sonde dropping run was commenced. During this high level run thin Ci was found to be invading from the south. It is thought that the cirrus will not impact the emissivity retrievals. It is hoped that the atmospheric profile measured with the dropsondes is characteristic of the profile during the low level runs.

The main instruments performed as expected with only the 50 GHz channel of Deimos giving poor performance. The sortie went almost precisely as planned barring the over-shooting of the F2E2 transect at the end of the sortie.

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.346** Date **19/2/08** Name **Chawn Harlow** Page **1** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
172518	T/O				Fairbanks
180318	P1				Commense
180903	P1	FL100			Inter.
181238	P1	"			Re commense
181735	P1	FL059			End
181953	R1.1	FL055			C2 D2
	R1.1				
182314	P2				5600' → 4000'
182507	P2/R1.2				E2 F2
					ARIES/SWS Zenith views
					During reposition F2 → C2
					Conditions very good with
					very little cloud at any level.
					MS2 watching UFC to note
					cloud presence.
183246	R2	4300'			End
					No Cloud; CPhys no particles
184040					Ice fog ahead
184658	R3				Start C2 D2
185010	R3				End
185207	R4				Start E2 F2
185957	R4				End
				Richard's	68° 39' 48.9 48.9" N
				Position	149° 8' 45.3" W
191417	R5	3700'			Start E1 D1

191715

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.346** Date 19/12/09 Name C Harlow Page 2 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
191517					
191715	R5				End
192008	R6	2800'			Start E1 → F1
192735	R6				End
194143	R7	3800'			Start C3 → D3
194444	R7				End
194706	R8	2000'			Start E3 → F3
195437	R8				End
					Repositions all at 5000'
					ARIES/SWS Zenith view
					Heimann Cals in Repositions
200902	R9	3700'			C → D Start
201154	R9				End
201421 201154	R10	2000'			Start G → H
					Snow deposition N-side of hills, scoured south side, protruding veg. in ravines, striations & drift patterns. Frozen lakes on N-S runs. Drift streaks E-W oriented N end of GH
202206	R10	2000'			End
202228	R10 P3	2000'			Start
2052		FL295			Contrailing
210557	R11	FL350			Start / End P3
Sonde 1	210634				

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.346** Date 19/2/08 Name C. Harlow Page 3 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
210936	Sonde 2	FL350			Still contrailing
2111					Cl below visible and ARIES can see
211149	R11				F2 → E2
211309	R12.2				D2 → C2 Start
Sonde 3	211316				Sonde 3
211557	R11.2				End Sat OP (2116z)
212605	R12.3	FL350			Start F2 → E2
212631	Sonde 4				Sonde 4
212901	Sonde 5				Sonde 5
212927	R11.3				End
213200					End of Science
					SWS - Lost 5 min in middle
					SHIMS - not well calibrated
					- check tomorrow
					C Phys - 2DC (noisy in cold fine at low level)
					ARIES - Good
					AVARS - Good sondes
					- GPS a little late
					Heimann - Good
					MARSS/Deimos - Good except 50 GHz at end

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B346

Date: 19 Feb 2008	Operator: JC	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	DAU3 Time:	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time:	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
16:00																SEADAS & SID1 time set	
162500	162500 after warm up, in hangar before push back pcasp vref = 9.00, flow 0.9 2dc ok 2dp ok seadas not yet logging sid1 running, not logging																
165300	165300 Seadas logging 2dc & 2dp switched off due refuelling activity sid 1 logging																
165600																2dc & 2dp restarted	
172518																T/O, heaters on	
173400																Entering cloud, snow	
173530	13	0.3		100		59	400	10000	0								
174700	31	0.27		100		38	650	5000	0							Transit, 2dp showind data but much noise	
175100	9	0.09		3		0	0	250	0							Out of top of cloud layer 2dp settles to low counts ok., but still somewhat noisy	
181800	10	0		0		0	0	0	0							End of P1, 2dp ok	

P Reference Volts =	FFSSP Reference Volts =	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B346

Date: 19 Feb 2008	Operator: JC	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	DAU3 Time:	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time:	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
181953	8	0		0		0	0	0	0							Start r1.1	
182200	6	0		0		0	0	0	0								
182300	10	0		0		0	0	0	0								
182313	12	0		0		0	0	0	0							Start p2	
182530	12	0		0		0	0	0	0							End p2 start 2.1	
183036	12	0		0		0	0	0	0								
183246	17	0		0		0	0	0	0							End run 2.1	
184710	10	0		0		0	0	0	0							Start r3	
185010	10	0		0		0	0	0	0							End r3	
185222	14	0		0		0	0	0	0							Start r4	
185957	20	0		0		0	0	0	0							End r4	
191417	10	0		0		0	0	0	0							Run 5	
191715	11	0		0		0	0	0	0							End run 5	
192008	13	0		0		0	0	0	0							Run 6	
192735	16	0		0		0	0	0	0							End run 6	
194143	6	0		0		0	0	0	0							Run 7	
194444	11	0		0		0	0	0	0							End run 7	
194706	13	0		0		0	0	0	0							Run 8	
195437	16	0		0		0	0	0	0							End run 8	
200902	6	0		0		0	0	0	0							Run 9	
201154	10	0		0		0	0	0	0							End run 9	
201421	13	0		0		0	0	0	0							Run 10	
202206	16	0		0		0	0	0	0							End run 10	
202228	16	0		0		0	0	0	0							Start profile 3	
	2dp turned off due noise.																

P Reference Volts =	FFSSP Reference Volts =	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B346

Date: 19 Feb 2008	Operator: JC	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	DAU3 Time:	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time:	Page 3 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
205750																Occasional noise on 2dc, fl320	
210557	3	0		0		0	0	off								Run 11.1	
210634																Sonde 1	
210937																Sonde 2	
211149	5	0		0		noise		off								End run 11.1	
211309	5	0		0		noise		Off								Run 11.2	
211306																Sonde 3	
211557	6	0		0		noise		off								End run 11.2	
212605	3	0		0		noise		off								Run 11.3	
212631																Sonde 4	
212903																Sonde 5	
212927	4	0		0		noise		off								End run 11.3	
213300 end of science, transit back to Fairbanks pcasp voltage 8.1																	
220000																Log to FM pc	

P Reference Volts =	FFSSP Reference Volts =	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =		

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B 346

T/O: 17:24:15

Date of Flight: 19/02/08

Land: 22:59:52

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		FFSSP not fitted
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown		NB Always use 0 and 240000 as times
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Note the calibration file used Total Glitches = Sec File written ok? Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit		Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		Note original and subsequent File sizes
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?		
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B346

Date: 19 Feb 2008

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Done	Zip data transferred from BADC To verify upload
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Done	B346 205309 blocks
6) In PVWAVE		Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'		Blocks read 47543
ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE		Blocks written 47543
a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat	205309	Bad reads 0
b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat		
iii) exit	205483	
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE		
a) Default directory: PMSDATA:		
b) Flight number: Bnnn		
c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat		
d) Comment string:		Note times
e) Start time: 0 if unknown	T/O – 5 min	
f) End time: 240000 if unknown	Land + 5 min	
g) Read 2DC: Y		Ignore error message scroll
h) Read 2DP: Y		Vestigial error from tapes
i) Secondary data: Y		
j) FSP-SYNC: Y		Check FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA
k) cmd.str: Y		And SEC files exist and have data
l) Auto time correction: N		done
m) Full length secondary: N		
8) 2D image display and printing		This must be done from Floods itself
Quick look at image blocks if required		Note any problems with images
In PVWAVE		
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'		
i) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY		
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:		
b) Flight number: Bnnn		
c) IWC plot: N		
d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP		
e) Start time: 0 if unknown		
f) End time: 240000 if unknown		
g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec		

Preparation of imagery for Core data product		
iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10	Creates files	Copy nos of pages to be produced [21] [28] Time to closest previous min
iv) exit PVWAVE	PMSDATA:	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_Bnnn_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		Note files are ascii
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	Done	
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO		NB an error message may Appear, floating point Exception, rerun and use Time quoted in error Message, repeat until
a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: 0 if unknown i) End time: 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D	T/O + 30sec Land – 30sec	Successful. Note time data processed up to Check 2dproc files present 2dc, 2dp and dat OK
10) In PVWAVE		Error message about HDDR File should be ignored.
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' iii) exit		Note records Note file size
11) MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		
12) CHECKS:		
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?		

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number:

Date:

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing		
Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW		Note the min size channel Note the volume flow rate
a) Flight number: Bnnn	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px; width: fit-content; margin: auto;"> Processing could not proceed beyond this point; asked for "full name of mfd" </div>	
b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT		
c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii)		
d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1 If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here		
e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs ⁻¹ (Calibration files to be stored in Exeter Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm3/sec		
f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d)		
g) Start time: 0 if unknown		
h) End time: 240000 if unknown		
3) In PVWAVE		
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'		
Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!		
ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat' , 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp'		
iii) exit		
4) MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp		
b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX		
c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name		
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		

B346_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

15:30:30.13 --- - - - -
15:30:30.14 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
15:30:30.14 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
15:30:30.14 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B346
15:30:30.14 --- - - - -
15:30:51.91 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
15:31:13.47 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
15:31:24.38 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
15:31:33.03 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
15:31:58.80 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:31:58.80 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:31:58.81 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:32:05.28 SWS - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
15:32:07.22 SWS - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
15:32:11.16 USH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
15:32:12.98 USH - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
15:32:22.37 LSH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
15:32:24.24 LSH - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
15:32:53.17 SWS 0.0 - - - Telescope stopped.
15:32:55.69 SWS 0.0 - - - Telescope sent to 118.658
15:32:57.35 SWS 118.6 - - - Telescope stopped.
15:33:35.23 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
15:33:42.68 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:33:42.77 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:33:43.06 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:33:49.12 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:33:49.31 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:33:49.51 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:34:10.95 SWS 123.7 - - - Telescope stopped.
15:34:12.36 SWS 123.7 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
15:34:17.92 SWS 123.7 - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
15:34:31.30 SWS 123.7 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
15:34:35.46 SWS 123.7 - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
15:34:46.98 SWS 123.7 - - - Telescope sent to 92.746
15:35:25.20 --- - - - - *** Note: activating web server disables motor
position indicator
16:12:11.08 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
16:12:14.90 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:12:21.34 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:12:26.02 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:12:26.14 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:12:26.15 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:12:32.47 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:12:32.67 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:12:32.87 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:12:52.03 --- - - - - *** Box temp +3c
16:51:14.90 LSH - - - - Idling
16:51:14.92 USH - - - - Idling
16:51:14.97 SWS - - - - Idling
16:51:23.24 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:51:23.24 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:51:23.25 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:51:29.69 SWS - - - - Idling
16:51:29.89 LSH - - - - Idling
16:51:30.09 USH - - - - Idling
16:51:34.85 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:51:34.85 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:51:34.87 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:51:52.88 --- - - - - *** Box temp -3c
16:55:54.25 SWS 123.7 - - - Telescope sent to 120.882
17:02:28.24 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
17:02:34.22 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:02:34.25 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:02:34.27 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:02:40.66 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:02:40.87 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

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17:02:41.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:02:56.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** Box temp -5c
17:29:18.61	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
17:29:23.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:29:23.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:29:23.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:29:29.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:29:29.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:29:30.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:29:38.48	SWS	123.7	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
17:29:58.57	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
17:29:58.58	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
17:30:04.45	USH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
17:30:04.46	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
17:30:08.89	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
17:30:08.91	LSH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
17:30:24.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:30:24.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:30:24.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:30:28.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:30:29.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:30:29.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:30:35.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:30:36.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:30:36.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:30:54.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** t/o at 1724
17:31:14.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -6c
17:38:53.79	SWS	123.7	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
17:42:27.42	SWS	123.7	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
17:42:39.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:42:39.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:42:39.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:42:43.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:42:44.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:42:44.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:42:50.65	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
17:42:56.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:42:56.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:42:56.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:43:01.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:43:01.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:43:01.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:43:40.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -7c
17:57:49.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:49.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:49.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:50.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:54.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:54.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:55.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:58:00.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:58:10.93	SWS	123.7	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
18:00:49.22	SWS	123.7	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
18:01:07.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:01:07.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:01:07.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:01:11.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:01:11.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:01:12.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:01:25.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -8c
18:03:37.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of P1 from FL160
18:17:45.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of P1
18:18:44.57	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
18:18:47.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:18:48.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:18:48.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:18:52.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:18:52.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:18:52.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

```

18:20:01.73 --- - - - - *** Start of Run 1.1
18:20:34.10 --- - - - - *** box temp -9c
18:23:19.66 --- - - - - *** End of Run 1.1
18:23:31.88 --- - - - - *** Start of P2
18:24:11.31 --- - - - - *** box temp -10c
18:25:12.06 --- - - - - *** edn P start run 1.2
18:33:07.77 --- - - - - *** end run
18:33:50.01 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
18:33:50.34 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
18:33:50.38 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
18:33:54.49 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
18:33:54.80 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
18:33:55.00 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
18:35:36.08 SWS 123.7 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
18:38:52.69 SWS 123.7 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
18:39:44.02 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
18:39:44.07 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
18:39:44.20 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
18:39:48.50 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
18:39:48.70 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
18:39:48.90 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
18:47:10.83 --- - - - - *** Start of R3
18:50:19.73 --- - - - - *** End of Run
18:50:42.65 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
18:50:42.70 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
18:50:42.92 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
18:50:47.14 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
18:50:47.36 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
18:50:47.53 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
18:52:08.61 --- - - - - *** Start of Run
18:59:59.54 --- - - - - *** end run 4
19:00:05.67 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:00:05.86 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:00:05.91 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:00:10.18 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:00:10.55 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:00:10.83 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:03:17.48 SWS 123.7 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
19:06:28.90 SWS 123.7 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
19:06:36.03 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:06:36.15 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:06:36.19 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:06:40.56 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:06:40.73 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:06:40.93 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:06:46.73 SWS - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
19:06:46.73 SWS - - - 200 - NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
19:06:51.24 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:06:53.79 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:14:19.71 --- - - - - *** Start of Run
19:17:32.84 --- - - - - *** End of Run5
19:18:21.78 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:18:21.88 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:18:21.92 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:18:24.49 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:18:26.28 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:18:26.79 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:20:11.33 --- - - - - *** Start of Run6
19:20:15.13 SWS 123.7 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
19:22:14.31 SWS 123.7 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
19:27:37.10 --- - - - - *** End of Run6
19:27:41.31 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:27:41.36 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:27:41.42 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:27:44.14 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:27:45.91 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:27:46.35 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:30:10.73 SWS 123.7 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
19:33:20.42 SWS 123.7 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000

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19:40:47.37 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:40:47.39 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:40:47.74 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:40:49.86 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:40:52.07 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:40:52.33 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:41:44.46 --- - - - - *** Start of Run7
19:44:45.93 --- - - - - *** End of Run
19:45:46.42 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:45:46.57 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:45:46.66 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:45:49.01 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:45:51.12 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:45:51.33 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:47:07.89 --- - - - - *** Start of Run8
19:52:46.37 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:52:48.82 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:52:56.87 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
19:52:56.88 SWS - - - 100 - NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
19:53:00.03 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:53:01.48 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:53:05.29 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
19:53:50.35 --- - - - - *** SWS NIR dropped out...
19:54:45.35 --- - - - - *** End of Run
19:55:02.63 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
19:55:19.80 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:56:36.85 --- - - - -
19:56:36.86 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
19:56:36.86 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
19:56:36.87 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B346
19:56:36.87 --- - - - -
19:56:40.74 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
19:56:45.18 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
19:56:47.25 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
19:57:41.64 --- - - - -
19:57:41.64 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
19:57:41.64 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
19:57:41.64 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B346
19:57:41.64 --- - - - -
19:57:55.03 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
19:57:59.35 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
19:58:01.59 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
19:58:44.97 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
19:58:46.63 SWS - - - 100 - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
19:58:51.76 USH - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 400ms.
19:58:53.46 USH - - - 400 - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 400ms.
19:58:57.20 LSH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
19:59:00.71 LSH - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
19:59:03.86 LSH - - - 400 - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 400ms.
19:59:06.50 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:59:06.50 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:59:06.51 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:59:07.30 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
19:59:07.87 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
19:59:08.13 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
19:59:08.82 SWS - - - - Idling
19:59:10.66 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
19:59:11.69 LSH - - - - Idling
19:59:11.95 USH - - - - Idling
19:59:14.79 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:59:14.79 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:59:14.82 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:59:16.63 SWS - - - - Idling
19:59:19.22 LSH - - - - Idling
19:59:19.43 USH - - - - Idling
19:59:20.60 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:59:20.60 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.

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19:59:20.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:59:30.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
19:59:37.99	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
20:01:35.41	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
20:01:37.08	SWS	169.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
20:03:16.55	SWS	123.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
20:09:09.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of Run 9
20:12:05.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of Run9
20:12:09.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:12:09.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:12:09.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:12:10.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
20:12:10.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
20:12:10.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
20:12:11.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:12:14.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:12:14.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:12:17.48	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
20:12:22.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:12:22.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:12:22.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:12:23.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:12:26.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:12:27.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:14:27.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of Run 10
20:22:08.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of Run
20:22:10.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:22:11.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:22:11.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:22:12.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:22:15.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:22:15.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:22:41.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of P3
20:33:44.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:33:44.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:33:44.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:33:46.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:33:49.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:33:49.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:33:53.45	LSH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 400ms.
20:33:58.11	LSH	-	-	-	600	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 600ms.
20:34:01.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:34:08.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:35:31.66	LSH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
20:35:35.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:35:40.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:36:49.32	LSH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 400ms.
20:36:53.14	LSH	-	-	-	600	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 600ms.
20:36:57.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:37:03.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:37:46.93	LSH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
20:37:49.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:37:54.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:47:28.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:47:28.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:47:28.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:47:30.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:47:30.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:47:30.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:47:31.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:47:34.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:47:34.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:47:37.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:47:37.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:47:37.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:56:55.78	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
20:57:00.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:57:02.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:57:04.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

```

20:57:04.75 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
20:57:05.71 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:57:10.16 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:06:18.65 --- - - - - *** End P Start of Run 11
21:11:36.28 --- - - - - *** end run
21:12:12.61 --- - - - - *** End of Run proprtly
21:12:30.77 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
21:12:36.87 LSH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
21:12:37.13 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:12:37.30 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:12:37.44 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:12:38.60 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:12:41.78 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:12:41.98 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:12:42.42 LSH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
21:13:12.64 --- - - - - *** start run 12
21:14:23.81 --- - - - - *** Run is actually 11.2...
21:16:02.98 --- - - - - *** end run
21:16:07.98 LSH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
21:16:43.31 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:16:43.43 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:16:43.68 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:16:44.76 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:16:47.97 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:16:48.20 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:16:52.06 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
21:16:56.04 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:16:56.19 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:16:56.22 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:16:57.71 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:17:00.51 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:17:00.91 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:22:01.90 --- - - - - *** start run
21:24:43.69 LSH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
21:25:08.01 LSH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
21:25:38.29 LSH - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
21:26:06.55 --- - - - - *** Real start of run...
21:26:53.80 USH - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
21:26:53.81 USH - - - 300 - NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
21:26:55.56 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:26:59.03 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:27:01.49 LSH - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
21:27:01.50 LSH - - - 300 - NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
21:27:03.75 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:27:07.22 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:29:39.90 --- - - - - *** End of Run 11.3
21:29:45.69 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:29:45.95 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:29:46.00 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:29:47.43 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:29:49.14 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:29:49.61 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:29:52.08 SWS 123.7 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
21:32:33.15 SWS 123.7 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
21:33:42.76 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:33:42.83 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:33:42.87 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:33:44.24 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:33:46.43 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:33:46.62 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:35:28.32 --- - - - - *** End of science, kit switched off
21:41:03.44 LSH - - - - Idling
21:41:03.46 SWS - - - - Idling
21:41:03.50 USH - - - - Idling
21:41:09.98 SWS - - - - Instrument closed.
21:41:11.69 USH - - - - Instrument closed.
21:41:13.27 LSH - - - - Instrument closed.
21:41:21.49 SWS - - - - Telescope disabled.
21:41:28.62 --- - - - - *** SHUTTING DOWN...

```

21:41:28.85 SWS - - - Telescope motor control quit.

Cal script ends on Ncd + 90°

ARIES flight log		Flight: <u>R46</u>	page <u>1</u> of <u> </u>
Date: <u>19/02/09</u>	Operator(s): <u>cbss</u>	Res: <u>1</u>	Gain A: <u>2</u> B: <u>2</u>
Loc./Notes: <u>CLPXII North Slope Alaska.</u>			

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
1410		Started	data				6990 DSR
155835	Grnd	1/120	HBB	cls	71-13	22-04	HBB Cal.
155949	Grnd	1/120	CBB	cls	71-13	22-05	CBB Cal.
173935	Trans 1	1/120	HBB	cls			CBB see to 20°C.
174155	Trans 2	1/120	HBB	cls	70-99	22-02	
174310	Trans 2	1/120	CBB	cls	70-69	22-25	
181905	R1-1	Cal script	Ncd	cls			G2 D2.
182024	R1-1	Ncd. s2d1	cls	cls	70-89	22-58	G2 D2 finished early
182328	R1-1	Cal script		cls	70-92	21-42	end.
182443	R1	Cal script		cls	70-76	22-74	Star
182545	R2	400/1	Ncd	cls	70-92	22-43	
182908	R2-2	Cal script		cls	70-89	22-87	Crop Cal finished early - sorry
183012	R2-2	400/1	Ncd	cls			693040 on Ncd + 90 sorry again.
183304	R2	R2 R2 Script		cls			After Hdr
183428	Reposition	Cal script		cls			
183559	Reposition	400/1	Zen	open	70-6	22-20	
183920	Reposition	Cal script		cls	71-26	22-50	
184522	In turn	Cal script		cls	71-15	22-50	
184659	R3 300	520/1	Ncd	cls	71-11	22-43	
190223	In turn	Cal script		cls	71-05	22-38	
190201	R4	400/1	Ncd	cls	70-86	22-08	
190523	R4	Cal script		cls	70-95	22-43	
190649	R4	400/1	Ncd	cls	70-23	22-46	
190600	Cal script			cls	71-18	22-54	recomputed brightness temp.
190217	Cal script			cls			
190335	R4	400/1	Zen	open	71-15	22-11	
190704	Cal script			cls	71-17	22-52	
191139	Cal script			cls	71-14	21-99	In turn @ Ncd start.
191402	R5	400/1	Ncd	cls	71-23	22-87	
191725	R5	Cal script		cls	70-95	22-33	
191934				cls	70-85	22-44	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B346

page 2 of

Date: 19/02/08 Operator(s): JSS

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B?

Loc./Notes: CLPX-II

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
192051	R5	Zen	open	open	709	22-21	240/1
192300	R6	Nce	clsd	clsd	7090	22-81	240/1
192500	R6	240/1	Nce	clsd	71-3	22-26	240/1
192710	endR6	CalScript		clsd	7087	22-33	
192918	Repos	CalScript		clsd	71-09	22-42	
193038	Repos.	Zen	400/1	open	70-89	22-44	
193403	Repos	CalScript		clsd	7091	22-03	
193520	Repos	Noise Script		clsd	71-07	22-26	HBB noise test
194012	R7skw	CalScript		clsd	71-14	22-2	
194139	R7	520/1	Nce	clsd	7076	22-47	
194455	endR7	CalScript		clsd	7090	22-50	
194709	R8	400/1	Nce	clsd	703	22-1	2200'
195045	R8	CalScript			7062	22-78	
195245	R8	400/1	Nce	clsd	7064	22-92	
195447	endR8	CalScript			71-01	22-77	
195643	Repos.	CalScript		clsd	71-04	22-30	
195800	Repos	Zen	open		7076	22-33	400/1
200243	Repos. 1/120	1/120	HBB	open	7066	22-39	} For Broghmans cal.
200253	Repos	1/120	CBB	open	7066	22-17	
200722	Repos	CalScript		clsd	71-60	22-29	
200849	R9	520/1	Nce	clsd	71-57	22-33	20 1150 ended run
201239	endR9	CalScript		clsd	7088	23-19	
201435	R10	400/1	Nce	clsd	7082	22-60	
201758	R10	CalScript		clsd	7076	22-43	
201930	R10	400/1	Nce	clsd	712	22-42	
202220	endR10	CalScript		clsd	7094	22-44	
20332		CalScript		clsd	71-06	22-52	
210552	R11	400/1	Nce	clsd	71-01	22-39	drop and c run FL350
210913	R11	CalScript			7062	22-43	
211032	R11	400/1	Nce	clsd	7073	22-92	FL350
211200	endR11	CalScript		clsd	7074	22-22	

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	19/02/08	Flight	B346	log pages	2
Operator(s)	Pollard		Campaign	CLPX-II			
Departure	Fairbanks		Arrival	Fairbanks			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						X	
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						X	
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						X	
FERA on					at time	15:15	
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	19.1	Ch	19.2	Ch18	18.3	
Temperature controller set points		50°C	17	50°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on					at time	15:18	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	291.4	Cold	291.5			
Target heating						X	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						X	
Scanning on (LMD box)					at time	15:19	
Scan indication	Monitor >			Visual			X

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						X	
Turn on Deimos CPU						X	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						X	
Start Deimos Software					at time	15:08	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	291.8	Cold	292.0			
Target heating						X	
Scan indication	Monitor x			Visual			X
Weather	Cloud				Precip		
	Surface				Pressure		
	Other						

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	N/A	at time	N/A	
Brightness temps 'sensible'					
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.5	Cold	294.6
	Deimos:	Hot	345	Cold	302.9
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B	
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	
	58.14	19.38	58.27	18.31	
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)
	40.67	35.08	37.48	42.57	42.46

Power changeover

Headset on before start	
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)	
Exit Deimos Software (x)	
POWER CHANGEOVER	
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton
Restart Deimos Software	
System running again	at time

CVI log

2/19/08 4:12:52 PM B346 CLPX-II
2/19/08 4:13:25 PM Lymann Hygro zeroed
2/19/08 4:17:26 PM Temperature on tip heater good (35), temp on sample flow F1 and
F2 reading above setpoint? (35.5 for F2 and 53.7 for F1)
2/19/08 5:50:18 PM Temp Flow and Liquide LEDs all out on CPC
2/19/08 5:52:07 PM PCASP apears to be ok
2/19/08 5:52:59 PM Lyman Hygro working ok, but signals less than zero.
2/19/08 6:11:41 PM Turn diluent on Lymann hygro down to 0
2/19/08 6:17:29 PM Flow LED back on on CPC during profile decent
2/19/08 6:19:44 PM start of run 1.1
2/19/08 6:22:51 PM Windows time adjusted to GPS time
2/19/08 8:54:51 PM Flow LED gone out on profile climb to 530
2/19/08 8:55:15 PM Flow LED gone out on CPC on profile climb to 530
2/19/08 9:06:49 PM Sorry, that should have been 350!
2/19/08 9:41:08 PM Zeroing Lymann Hygrometer
2/19/08 10:11:03 PM Lymann Hygrometer diluent increase to 0.1

Flight:

B346

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:	Not Fitted
Heimann:	OK
Deiced Temp:	OK
Non-deiced Temp:	OK

Hygrometers

FWVS:	OK
General Eastern:	OK
Johnson Williams:	OK
Nevezorov:	OK
Total Water Probe:	OK

Cameras

Downward Facing:	OK
Forward Facing:	OK
Rearward Facing:	OK
Upward Facing:	OK

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:	Fitted, Not Operated
GIN Applanix:	OK
INU Honeywell:	OK
Radar Altimeter:	OK
RVSM IAS:	OK
RVSM Static Pressure:	OK
XR5 GPS:	OK

Report Created 12/03/2008
15:06:58

Misc Core

AMTG:	OK
AVAPS:	OK
Cabin Pressure:	OK
Fax machine:	Fitted, Not Operated
Printer:	OK
S9 Static Pressure:	OK
Satcom C:	OK
Satcom H:	OK
Turb Centre-Static:	OK
Turb Left Right:	OK
Turb Up-Down:	OK
Turb Horizontal Chk:	OK
Turb Vertical Chk:	OK
Weather Radar:	Fitted, Not Operated

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:	OK
DLU BBR Lower:	OK
DLU BBR Upper:	OK
DLU Core Chem:	OK
DLU Core Consoles:	OK
DLU Port Aft:	OK
DLU Port Fwd:	Not Fitted
DLU Stbd Fwd:	Not Fitted

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:	OK
BBR (IR) Lower:	OK
BBR (red) Lower:	OK

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:	Minor Problems
BBR (IR) Upper:	OK
BBR (red) Upper:	Minor Problems

ARIES:	OK
DEIMOS:	Minor Problems
IR Camera:	Not Fitted
JNO2 Lower:	Not Fitted
JNO2 Upper:	Not Fitted
JO1D Lower:	Not Fitted
JO1D Upper:	Not Fitted
MARSS:	OK
SHIMS Lower:	OK
SHIMS Upper:	OK
SWS:	Minor Problems
TAFTS:	Not Fitted

Last Updated:

20/02/2008 20:26:20

Cloud Probes

2DC:	Minor Problems
2DP:	Duff Data
FFSSP:	Not Fitted
PCASP:	OK
2DS:	Not Fitted
ADA:	Not Fitted
CAPS:	Not Fitted
CCN:	Not Fitted
CDP:	Not Fitted
CIP 100:	Not Fitted
CIP 25:	Not Fitted
CPI:	Not Fitted
CVI:	OK
SID1:	OK
SID2:	Not Fitted

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:	OK
Filters 47mm:	Fitted, Not Operated
Filters 90mm:	Not Fitted
Neph - Dry:	OK
Neph - Wet:	OK
PSAP:	Fitted, Not Operated
AMS:	Not Fitted
CPC 3025 (AMS):	Not Fitted
INC:	Not Fitted
VACC:	Not Fitted
CPC 3010A (CVI):	OK

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:	OK
NOx TE42C:	OK
Ozone TE49C:	OK
Ozone TE49:	Not Fitted
SO2 TE43C:	Fitted, Not Operated
TDLAS (NIR) CH4:	Duff Data
TDLAS (NIR) CO2:	OK
FAGE:	Not Fitted
Formaldehyde:	Not Fitted
NOx FAAM:	Not Fitted
NOxy:	Not Fitted
ORAC:	Not Fitted
PAN:	Not Fitted
PERCA:	Not Fitted
Peroxide:	Not Fitted
PTRMS:	Not Fitted
TDLAS (1C):	Not Fitted
WAS Bags:	Not Fitted
WAS Bottles:	Not Fitted

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:	Not Fitted
LIDAR:	Not Fitted
LTI:	Not Fitted
SAW Hygrometer:	Fitted, Not Operated

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B346

Date: 19 February 2008

Instruments

1. IIU – T4 messages counting up on pre-flight. Reset IIU CB then okay.
2. HORACE – Option to Align INU to GPS posn presents XR5M Longitude as *****. Too big a number for the settings?
3. Video – Can't select individual cameras at Aft Core Console
4. DEIMOS – Channel 50GHz noise towards end
5. SWS – Sensitivity may be a bit low, will do calibration check tomorrow
6. Cloud Physics – 2DC slightly noisy at high level. 2DP switched off above Fl250 as noisy.
- 7.

TWC Zero level = 2046 DRSU

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

Nil connections

Satcom-H Calls

OBR x 1 to Richard at Ground Site.

Issues

Cabin very warm at start (to keep galley & toilet water from freezing). Got to 28C at ARIES Rack. down.

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

^ Clipboard power button

Date: 10/2/08

Flight No: B 346

Pre-Flighter: AMW

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
Aircraft Cabin: Power-up				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	<u>Done</u>
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	<u>IN HANGAR - NO SAITS</u>
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	<u>Done</u>
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	<u>Done</u>
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up & on AUTO	<u>JOS</u>
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input type="checkbox"/>			
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
28	<input type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
External Checks				
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	<u>n/r</u>
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
41	<input type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
42	<input type="checkbox"/>	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
43	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
44	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Avalon Checks				<u>Signed</u>
	<input type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
	<input type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more
	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

Flight B346 21:09:28

Heading 189 deg Speed 372 knots Height 35.0kft Press 238mb

Lat 68°54.0'N Long 148°54.0'W Wind 48 ms-1/ 230 deg

Temp -58.1C Dewpoint -65.54C

From 20:17:58 to now

Current values		
INS WIND ANGLE	230.85	deg
INS WIND SPEED	48.52	m s-1

Flight B346 17:48:41

Heading 355 deg Speed 289 knots Height 16.4kft Press 539mb

Lat 66°30.0'N Long 148°18.0'W Wind 15 ms-1/ 171 deg

Temp -22.4C Dewpoint -22.1C

From 17:07:00 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	539.38	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-22.41	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-22.1	deg C

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B346:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as any PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	01 Apr 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x for/Upward Facing Cameras

3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Jonathan P. Taylor

Manager Atmospheric Radiation Research Group
Met Office
Cordouan 2 W079
FitzRoy Road
Devon
EX1 3PB
UK

Tel: +44 (0)1392 884647

Fax: +44 (0)1392 885681

E-mail: jonathan.p.taylor@metoffice.gov.uk